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Employee Participation In Decision Making And Productivity Of Plastic Manufacturing Firms In Anambra State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This work examined the effect of employee participation in decision making on employee productivity in plastic manufacturing firms in Anambra State, Nigeria. The study aimed to determine the influence of employees' consultation on employee effectiveness; collective bargaining on employee efficacy and employee delegation on production timelines in plastic manufacturing firms in Anambra State, Nigeria. Relevant theoretical and empirical literatures were examined. This study is anchored on Democratic Participatory Theory and Goal setting theory. Survey design was adopted. The study was carried out in Anambra State, Nigeria. The population of the study consisted 1648 employees of plastic manufacturing firms Anambra State. The statistical formula devised by Borg and Gall was employed to determine the sample size of 321. The instrument used for the study was questionnaire. Face and content validity was adopted while, test re-test and Cronbach Alpha method was carried out to achieve reliability of instruments. Simple percentage analysis was employed to answer the research questions. Linear regression analysis was employed to test the hypotheses. The result showed that employee consultation had a significance positive effect on employee effectiveness; collective bargaining had a significant positive effect on employee efficacy; employee delegation has a significant influence on production timelines in plastic manufacturing firms in Anambra State, Nigeria. The study concluded that employee participation on decision had a positive significant effect on employee productivity. The study recommended that management plastic firms should make it a part of its standard policy to ensure all employees opinions, suggestions, view are subjected to their merit and accepted where applicable after employees' consultation. Management of plastic firms and employees should explore options together; be open to the ideas that a third position exists and that they can get to the idea jointly through collective bargaining on decision making. Employees should be allowed to make contribution in policy development as they play a major role in policy implementation and this among others will increase organizational productivity through employee delegation. The study contributed to knowledge by updating the existing conceptual, theoretical, extant and empirical literatures. The study also provides empirical evidence that can aid manufacturing firms, other companies and policy formulators in understanding the effect of employee participation on decision making on organizational productivity.

Keywords: Employee Consultation, Collective Bargaining, Employee Delegation, Employee Effectiveness, Employee Efficacy and Production Timelines

INTRODUCTION

The solid foundation of any successful company is its employee. Employee represent a source of knowledge and ideas, but oftentimes that resource remains untapped (Miller, 2014). Involving employee in the decision-making process not only empowers them to contribute to the success of an organization, but also saves the company time and money in increased productivity and reduced outsourcing. Therefore, this study is about assessing the effectiveness of productivity with the participation of employee in decision making. The main reason for conducting this study is to know if employee participation in decision making can lead to the effectiveness of productivity in an organization. Konings (2016) stated that productivity is an overall measure of the ability to produce goods and services. More specifically, productivity is the measure of how specified resources are managed to accomplish timely objectives as stated in terms of quantity and quality. Productivity may also be an index that measures output (goods and services) relative to the input labour, materials and energy used to produce the output. Therefore, a productivity measure describes how well the resources of an organization are being used to produce goods and services. Productivity is useful as a relative measure of actual output of production compared to the actual input of resources, measured across time or against common entities. As output increase for a level of input, or as the amount of input decreases for a constant level of output an increase in productivity occurs, (Konings 2017). Basically, participation of employee describes the involvement of employee in decision making which is concerned with shared decision making in the work situation (Mitchell, 2017). According to Noah (2019) participation of employee is a special form of delegation in which the subordinate gain greater control, freedom of choice with respect to bridging the communication gap between the management and workers.

Participation is the process whereby employees are involved in decision making processes, rather than simply acting on orders (Miller, 2014). Collective bargaining is a process for empowering employees to participate in managerial decision-making and improvement activities appropriate to their levels in the organization. Participation of employee describes the involvement of employee in decision making which is concerned with shared decision making in the work situation (Mitchell, 2016). Wagner, (2016) reported that employee participation is positively related to performance, satisfaction, and productivity of an employee. Several studies have identified employees' collective bargaining in decision making as an important high performance (Arthur, 2019). Employee participation is very vital because employee participation promote organizational peace in the concern, satisfy the desire of workers for self-expression and raise productivity, production and efficiency of workers.

Employee participation leads to efficiency and effectiveness and effectiveness in an organization, which inevitably causes productivity in an organisation (Miller, 2014). Participation in the decision-making process gives each employee the opportunity to voice their opinions, and to share their knowledge with others (Lundgrem, 2019). While this improves the relationship between manager and employee, it also encourages a strong sense of teamwork among workers. The expression of viewpoints opens dialogue between co-workers, with each worker bringing their individual strengths to a project. It is also a good way to gather information about the employees as to how they work in a team environment, and where training may be necessary, all of which leads to an increase in effectiveness, and ultimately an increase in good teamwork and performance. Decision making in many organizations were done by top management team without considering the input of the employees at the other managerial levels (Lester, 2018). In these organizations the decisions taken by top management were however implemented by the lower level of employees. Because lower management does not take part in the decision making, it sometimes becomes difficult for some of the decisions taken by top management to be implemented especially when the decisions seem not to be favourable hence, affecting productivity in an organization. Lundgrem, (2019) argues that flatter management and decentralized authority structures carry the potential for achieving outcomes unattainable by the traditional top down bureaucratic structures.

Lester (2018) opined that when employees are involved in making decisions, they gain a professional and personal stake in the organization and its overall success. This commitment leads to increased productivity as employees are actively participating in various aspects of the company and wish to see

their efforts succeed overall. This is not only beneficial to company growth, but is also on-the-job training for workers. The increase in responsibility expands employee skill sets, preparing them for additional responsibility in the future. Organisations have different types of decisions which they make in order to be effective in productivity and some of the decisions include short time, medium decisions and long-time decisions depending on the goals the organisation wants to achieve. Participation of workers in decision-making process has resulted in successful value creation in many organizations (Globe 2022). Though the extent to which employees should participate in organizational decision making is still a matter of debate. Some say that workers' union should participate with management as equal partners while some believe in restricted or bounded participation, that is, participation of employees or workers to a limited extent. However, there are a number of ways through which employees can participate in decision-making process of any organization. Elvis (2023) ascertained that one of the ways in which employees participate in decision making was through complete control. This is called the system of self-management where workers union acts as management. Through elected boards, they acquire full control of the management. In this style, workers directly deal with all aspects of management or industrial issues through their representatives. Bisocos (2020) postulate that participation through collective bargaining was another way in which employees take part in decision making. Collective bargaining refers to the participation of workers through collective agreements and by deciding and following certain rules and regulations. Collective bargaining in decision making is very critical to the survival of every organization and therefore needs serious attention to be able to address this attitude and ensure harmony in employer-employee relationship. Most organizations that ignored the inputs of employees, have largely experienced lots of turbulence, laxity, high rate of absenteeism and resignations, which impacts have and negative consequences on the organizational efficiency, effectiveness, and productivity. Participation in management initiatives motivates employees to deliver quality services to customers and improve organizational productivity (Bendix, 2018). Carson (2015) believes that an average employee learns under proper conditions and that through proper leadership, management motivates employees and makes them more productive.

A leader who uses participation creates benefits for an organization and its employees, as participation improves productivity of an organization and reduces role conflicts, role uncertainty, absenteeism and employees' turnover (Mendes & Stander, 2021). Modern organizations can no longer be managed successfully by the few people in authority. Now, with the emergence of the theories of participative management and with increasing recognition of workers input, employees more often have valuable contributions to make beyond the acceptable limits of their normal schedules. Many companies are now actively engaging employees more than ever in decisions making. The employee on the other hand expects to be asked how he feels about his job, and what his ideas are on how best to carry out particular tasks.

Statement of the Problem

The issue of whether participation of employee in decision making exists in the Nigerian industrial set-up is very controversial. Some managers firms in Nigeria do not practice participatory decision making. On the contrary, some management in Nigeria are of the opinion that participatory decision making does not exist and where it does it is not really practiced. Their reason is that the necessary prerequisites for participative decision in Nigeria are not available (lack of employee collective bargaining, employee delegation, employee engagement and employee commitment). Involving employee in decisions may improve the quality of productivity and acceptance of decisions when participation fits the constraints of the situation. Employee are operators and in position to know the challenges in successful execution of particular tasks. They also know the best solutions to problems arising from them. Some of the managers feel that the decision making process is their sole right and as such should be protected. Top management likes to remain formal in approach to employee so as to build air of importance around them. Some managers adopt leadership style that does not permit participation of their employee in decision making. Effectiveness of productivity with the participation of employee in decision making has been said to be a big problem in developing countries like Nigeria because some of the conflicts occur due to ineffective

workers participation in decision making that might lead to misunderstanding between workers and management. Ineffective participation in decision making on productivity is caused by some factors like lack of support from top management which hinders their participation. It also brings about misunderstanding to workers in their day to day activities due to unclear policies induced by the top management without any consultation made to them. Ineffective participation in decision making on productivity can cause conflicts within an organization. It leads to poor performance and delays in the work environment. Thus there should be a need for better understanding of the impact of employee participation on productivity so that organizations may have better performance, productivity and employee can be job satisfied. The manufacturing firms in Anambra State like other organization is faced with issues concerning participative management and organizational productivity. Scientists and researchers have cited a lack of an enabling environment and facilities that do not support transfer and implementation of modern technology, lack of exposure and mentorship and non-involvement of employee in decisions that affect their job. Over the years employee have cited poor innovation management capacity, lack of funds to adopt modern technologies and an organizational culture that lacks collective bargaining in organizational initiatives as a priority thereby hampering productivity.

A number of related studies on employee participation in decision making in various countries have been conducted. The results revealed that there was no genuine participation by employee in most organizations. The existing studies were mostly examined from a management point of view and not so much from employee's perspective. Therefore the results of the current study would yield different outcomes and their findings may not apply in the current context because none of the previous researchers have studied effects of employee collective bargaining and organizational productivity in manufacturing firms in Anambra State, Nigeria. These gaps in knowledge thus necessitated the proposed study and given the critical role that employee play in organizations. It is these problems that caught the researcher's attention to investigate more on employee participation in decision making from the prisms of employee' consultation, collective bargaining, delegation, engagement and commitment with regards to organizational productivity in plastic manufacturing firms in Anambra State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

This study investigated the effect of employee participation in decision making, on organizational productivity in plastic manufacturing firms in Anambra State, Nigeria..

The specific objectives of study were to:

- i. Examine the effect of employee consultation on employee effectiveness in plastic manufacturing firms in Anambra State, Nigeria.
- ii. Determine the influence of employee collective bargaining on employee efficacy in plastic manufacturing firms in Anambra State, Nigeria.
- iii. Investigate the effect of employee delegation on production timelines in plastic manufacturing firms in Anambra State, Nigeria.

Research Questions

In line with the objectives the following research questions were formulated

- i. To what level does employee consultation affect employee effectiveness in plastic manufacturing firms in Anambra State, Nigeria?
- ii. To what degree does employee collective bargaining influence employee efficacy in plastic manufacturing firms in Anambra State, Nigeria?
- iii. To what magnitude does employee delegation influence product timelines in plastic manufacturing firms in Anambra State, Nigeria?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated to achieve the objectives of the study:

Ho₁: Employee consultation has no significant positive effect on employee effectiveness in plastic manufacturing firms in Anambra State, Nigeria.

Ho₂: Employee collective bargaining has no significant positive effect on employee efficacy in plastic manufacturing firms in Anambra State, Nigeria.

Ho₃: Employee delegation has no significant positive influence on production timelines in plastic manufacturing firms in Anambra State, Nigeria.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Conceptual Review

Employee Participation

Several management strategies have been developed to enable organizations attain their objectives, one of which is participatory management. Participative Decision Making means employee participation in decision making. Both are used interchangeably in this paper. Employee Participation or Involvement is defined as a process of involving and empowering employees to use their input towards creating value and improving organizational productivity (Sofijanov & Chatleska, 2023). Employee participation also mean direct involvement or engagement of employees towards applying ideas, expertise, and efforts in solving organizational problems and achieving its goals or objectives. Adeola (2014) defines participation in decision-making as the active involvement of subordinates or followers in the making decisions that directly affect them in the work place. Participation in decision making is generally regarded as a sign of enlightened and democratic management. It may be through giving and receiving of information, achieve and suggestion and the sharing of experience among members of an organization. Murew (2017) opined that participation decision-making particularly applies to allowing the employees) to have a voice in shaping policies, procedures and processes that directly or indirectly affect employee participation. It is therefore a process of sharing among managers and employees. Though the use of participation also, individual members are involved in a wide range of objective setting, problem solving, and decision-making activities of the organization.

Davis (2021) stated that participation in decision-making is a mental and emotional involvement of persons in group situations that encourage them to contribute to group goals and share responsibility for them. Lewin (2019) defined it as a mode of organizational operation in which decision as to activities are arrived at by the person, who are to execute those decisions. However, participation from my own point of view, I can say is a process in which two or more parties influence each other in making decisions. The parties to the decision making process may be in their capacities as individuals or as groups. In participatory management, management selectively shares, some of its powers with employees. It takes into consideration the wishes and suggestions of the members as well as those of the leader. It is a human relations approach where all members of the group are seen as important contributors to the firm's decisions. Gurin, Veroff and Feld (2019) concluded that participation is really a middle-class value, and grows out of the prior expectations of those being supervised.

Decision Making: When defining the management the most important share is the decision making which is the most challenging and most important management function. Decision maker is the most important role. Managers within organizations make decisions based on everything within an organization does. Decisions are the ideas which turn into action and can have a positive or a negative impact. Decision making are taken under uncertainty and under a risk. The decision making process depends largely on knowledge, experience, skills attitudes and values etc of decision maker. Store and Freeman (2014) Decision making is defined as “the process of identifying and selecting a course of action to solve a particular problem.” It can also be defined as a thought process of selecting a logical choice from the available options in decision making process. Studies have showed that employee participation is positively related to performance, satisfaction and productivity of an employee. Participation in decision making make employees gain self-actualization hence increases employees’ motivation and job performance. Researcher Moorhead and GrifCin (2014) decision making is defined as selecting between alternative’s which considered as an outcome of mental process which primary to the selection of an action among alternatives. Decision making kid of mapping the consequences of decisions work with the individual factors and choosing the best option or action. Decision making process decision makers options or actions directed by a goal. The several alternative courses of action is linked to various outcomes.

Employee Consultation: Consultative participation can potentially touch all workers directly in relation to their work tasks, work organization and working conditions. Such participation is strongly contingent on a voluntary management decision and can be seen as HRM practices (Kuye & Sulaimon, 2021). Consultative participation appears to have an impact on organizational productivity in three rather basic ways. First, employees with consultative participation opportunities can influence organizational productivity directly by offering suggestions leading to more efficient processes or better product quality (Koech & Namusonge, 2022). In doing so, employees can contribute to higher labour productivity and process innovation.

Collective Bargaining: Collective bargaining means that every employee is regarded as a unique human being, not just a cog in a machine, and each employee is involved in helping the organization meet its goals (Nwoko & Emerole, 2017). Nachiket (2014) views collective bargaining as ‘a range of processes designed to engage the support, understanding and optimum contribution of all employees in an organization and their commitment to its objectives’ to enable them contribute to the continuous improvement and the ongoing success of their work. Agyeman (2022) sees collective bargaining as a unique human being not just a part in a machine and each employee is involved in helping the organization meet its goals. He further explained that each employee’s input is solicited and valued by his or her management. Employees and management recognize that each employee is involved in running the business. According to Pyman (2015), the involvement of employees in the organizational operations not only motives them but also enables them to contribute more effectively and efficiently.

Employee Delegation: Delegation is described as being at a higher level of subordinates’ involvement in a continuum of decision procedures (Yuki, 2022). Although some studies have defined it as a distinct set of decision-making procedures, others consider it to be a type of Participative Decision Making (PDM). However, most have argued that they are distinct constructs indicating that PDM is a means of power sharing, whereas delegation is an alternative that involves power relinquishment (Leana, 2016). He noted that delegation ‘focuses on developing individual autonomy rather than on engendering democracy, that is, participative processes. It is associated with a process that allows employees working in an organization hierarchy ‘temporary authority’ to make decisions. (Sagie & Koslowsky 2018) It is also defined as ‘the assignment of new responsibilities to subordinates and additional authority to carry them out’ (Yuki 2022).

Organizational Productivity

Productivity is a measurement or calculation between input and outputs. Inputs are the amount of resources such as human resource, money, time, physical, technological and effort spent working in the organization, while output was the result. If the inputs are equivalent to the outputs, the worker is considered productive. When the organization are productive, they accomplish more in a given amount of time. In turn, efficiency saves their company money in time and labour. When employees are unproductive, they take longer time to complete projects, which cost employee’s more money due to the time lost (Ikeanyibe, 2019). The importance of higher productivity of the employees in manufacturing firms cannot be overemphasized, which include the following; Higher incomes and profit; Higher earnings; Increased supplies of both consumer and capital goods at lower costs and lower prices; Ultimate shorter hours of work and improvements in working and living conditions; Strengthening the general economic foundation of workers (Nwachukwu, 2018).

The existence of any organization is anchored on productivity and its importance cannot be overemphasized. It is the wish of every organization to be productive because productivity forms the cardinal essence for which every organization exist. To attain or increase productivity has led many organizations into constant reshuffling practice. This is in line with Simon (2017) when he rightly noted that “the issue of productivity has been instrumental to most repositioning exercises that go on from time to time in many organizations”. In fact productivity has often become the most central, contentious and analytical issues in all organizations be it public or private.

Productivity refers to the real output per unit of labor. It is a powerful driver of international capital flows. Productivity levels seem to be the highest in United States as compared to the euro area, because of

higher employment rates in U.S. (Skoczylas & Tissot, 2015). Meneze (2016) defined productivity as the employee's ability to produce work or goods and services according to the expected standards set by the employers, or beyond the expected standards. Productivity is calculated by comparing total amount of output to the total amount of input used to produce this output (Bojke 2022). Productivity is defined by Amah (2016) as the measure of how efficiently and effectively resources (inputs) are brought together and utilized for the production of goods and services (outputs) of the quality needed by society in the long term. This implies that productivity is a combination of performance and economic use of resources.

Employee effectiveness: Employee effectiveness means 'doing the right things or occupying oneself with the right things. The concept 'effectiveness' is linked to the assumption that organizations are goal-oriented (Cameron, 1986). The focus is on the actual attainment of organizational goals and not so much on the means necessary to reach them or the speed at which they are reached. For this reason, not everything that is effective has to be efficient; but everything that is efficient has to be effective (Georgopoulos & Tannenbaum 2017). Employee effectiveness is essential for improving results; and in order to perform effectively, clarity is needed. If your employees do not know what results are expected of them, there is a risk that they will work but will not perform. They are not doing the right things and so contribute insufficiently to the success of your organization (Cameron, 2014). Working effectively and efficiently are clear signs of good performance, although variables are interdependent. But not only do the variables influence each other, they also influence and are influenced by other factors. Role clarity, for instance, is key for employees to be able to work effectively and efficiently (Glunk & Wilderom 2016).

Employee Efficiency: Employee efficiency is about building a team or having individual employees who have a track record for making time, resources, and energy count for maximum output. A major metric used to measure employee efficiency is the amount of time or resources put into a specific task compared to the result achieved. Efficient employees make more money for their employers (Doucouliagos, & Laroche, 2022). One of the ways a business becomes more profitable is when the cost of production this includes both time and resources is reduced. Employee efficiency means hard and smart work. Employees often have to stretch themselves beyond assumable limits to get maximum output. As a result, employees acquire new skills and competencies (Ghemawat & Ricart 2023). This often leads to more efficiency. One way to improve employee efficiency is by promoting causes that help boost their physical for example telecommuting work from home/remote work. On the surface, one could argue against this because how can you guarantee that an employee is productive when they are out of sight. Efficiency is the ability to act or produce effectively with a minimum of waste, expenditure or unnecessary effort. The focus is on the resources and speed with which organisational goals are achieved (Drucker, 2014). Many companies' returns are under pressure. This makes it important that employees carry out the correct tasks (effective) in the right way (efficient). By working efficiently, more can be produced with the same amount of input (resources). In short, achieving more for lower costs, a higher return and less pressure.

Production Timelines: Production Timeline means the schedule of dates provided to the client outlining the various stages of the works. The Production timeline will be adjusted where changes are requested and/or required. Measures whether a unit of work was done correctly and on time. Criteria must be established to define what constitutes timeliness for a given unit of work. The criterion is usually based on customer requirements. A timeline is a display of a list of events in chronological order (Grafton & Rosenberg 2020). It is typically a graphic design showing a long bar labelled with dates paralleling it, and usually contemporaneous events. Timelines can use any suitable scale representing time, suiting the subject and data; many use a linear scale, in which a unit of distance is equal to a set amount of time. This timescale is dependent on the events in the timeline. A timeline of evolution can be over millions of years, whereas a timeline attacks can take place over minutes, and that of an explosion over milliseconds. An alternative option for measuring productivity is by monitoring the time it takes to complete a task. To do this, use productivity measuring software or online programs. One commonly used time management system requires employees to enter the time they spend on a task into a spreadsheet. The results can then be assessed by managers over time to see whether productivity is increasing, decreasing or remaining

steady. The advantage of this method is that modern software allows companies to break down time into minutes and even seconds to ensure that labor time is being used effectively.

Theoretical Review

This study is anchored on Democratic Participatory Theory by Rosseau (1956) and Goal setting theory postulated by Edwin Locke in 1960.

Democratic Participatory Theory: The Democratic Participatory Theory emphasizes on conditions which are necessary for effective participation and functions performed by participation to the individuals and society. For instance, Rosseau (1956) contended that through participation in decision making, the individual sense of freedom is increased since it gives the worker a very real degree of control over the course of his life and structure of his environment. Again, it serves to increase the value of individual freedom by enabling him to be his own master. Mills (1965) sees the industry as an area where the individual could gain experience in the management of the collective just as he could in government. The theory viewed the political arena as a kind of market place in which individuals constantly attempt to maximize the benefits and minimize losses they could gather from the political process. It assumes that man is selfish in the sense that each participant would be motivated by the desire to protect or enhance his own personal interest.

Relevance of this theory to the study: The theory assumes that increased participation is likely to increase the feeling of efficiency that ordinary citizens possess. This helps to increase the potential so that their actions can have an effect on public policy and lead to a greater sense of control over their communal lives. In essence, greater participation in one sense of life leads to greater participation in other spheres, *i.e.*, the workplace (Pateman, 1970).

Goal Setting Theory: Goal setting theory was postulated by Edwin Locke in 1960 and he asserted that goal setting is fundamentally linked to performance (Locke, 1968). Goal Setting Theory is an intellectual hypothesis of motivation grounded on the assertions that goals do regulate employee behavior. Goal theory postulates a positive link between performance and goal difficulty, with challenging goals eliciting much effort than simple goals (Martin and Manning, 1995). This hypothesis presupposes that behavior is purposeful and that goals focus employees' energies in performing specific task (Locke & Latham, 1990). Consequently, Goal Setting hypothesis is an effective strategy of arousing performance by provision of feedback, collective bargaining and participation (Latham et al, 2022).

Relevance of this theory to the study: Necessary feedback of results and collective bargaining in goal setting directs the employee behaviour and contributes to higher performance than absence of feedback and non-involvement. Also, specific, difficult goals lead to participation through collective bargaining in goal setting, enhanced employer-employee relations and improved performance by producing higher levels of effort and planning (Latham et al (2022). Thus goal setting can be an effective method of influencing performance by enhancing collective bargaining initiatives through provision of appropriate communication and regular feedback mechanism (Latham et al 2022).

Empirical Review

Chimaobi, (2022) the effect of employees' consultation in decision making on employee effectiveness using Afam Power Plc in Port-Harcourt, River State as a case study. The population of study comprised of managers and employees of the selected firm in Port-Harcourt River state. The sample for the study was given as 125. Out of the 125 questionnaire administered to the participant only 100 were returned while 25 were not returned. The study was analyzed using of tables and percentage while the three hypotheses were tested with the aid of ANOVA. The result revealed that employees' consultation in decision making has positive effect on employee effectiveness. This study recommends the following; organizations are encouraged to increase the frequency and level of employees' consultation in decision making between manager and subordinates to partake in joint decision making for the overall well-being of the organization. Again, firms are advised to structure their organization in such a way that it will

encourage free flow of decision making in every level of management to promote employee consultation in decision making and create effectiveness on organizational decision making process.

Uwandu, Udo-Anyanwu, and Okorie (2022) focused on of employees' consultation in decision making on employee effectiveness of library staff in Federal Universities in South- East Geo-political Zone of Nigeria. Two research questions and two null hypotheses guided the study. Correlation research design which involved simple linear method was adopted for the study. The population of the study is 332 library staff. Using total enumeration sampling technique, the entire population was adopted as sample for the study. Rating scale was used to collect data for the study. Pearson r statistics was used to answer the research questions while t test of significance of simple linear correlation statistics was used to test the hypotheses at $p < 0.05$ level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that of employees' consultation in decision making are highly and significantly related with employee effectiveness of library staff in Federal Universities in Anambra State Geo-political Zone of Nigeria. Based on the above findings, the researchers recommended that university management and university library management should incorporate the library staff in taking decisions concerning them and the affairs of the library.

Owolabi and Abdul-Hameed (2021) examined the relationship between collective bargaining in decision making and firms' productivity in the manufacturing sector in Nigeria. Data were generated by means of questionnaires to 670 manufacturing firms on collective bargaining in decision making and productivity variables. Responses from the survey were statistically 'analysed using descriptive statistics, product moment correlation, regression analysis and Z-test (approximated with the independent samples t-test). The results of the study indicate a statistically significant relationship between collective bargaining in decision making and firms' productivity as well as reveal a significant difference between the productivity of firms whose collective bargaining in decision making are deep and the productivity of firms whose collective bargaining in decision making are shallow. The findings also reveal the involvement of participating firms in collective bargaining in decision making. The implications of this study include the need for manufacturing firms to demonstrate high level of commitment to collective bargaining in decision making for productivity enhancement.

Osazevaru and Amawhe (2022) explored employees' collective bargaining in decision making and organizational effectiveness of manufacturing firms. The cross-sectional survey research design was employed. Data were elicited from the middle and lower level employees of manufacturing firms registered under the Manufacturing Association of Nigeria (M.A.N.), Edo/Delta. For the purpose of the research, ten firms were selected with a total staff population of 1,839. Taro Yamane's formula was used in arriving at a sample of 329 employees and 216 responses retrieved were analyzed using the simple percentage, mean statistics, and hypotheses tested with linear regression after multi-collinearity test and correlation matrix revealed no collinearity problem. Results of hypotheses tested showed that employees' collective bargaining in decision making has significant effect on organizational productivity, organizational adaptability, and organizational flexibility. Accordingly, the study recommended that the top management level of manufacturing firms should see the need to constantly involve the middle and lower level employees in their decision making processes whether directly or through advisory participation, to continually gain more effectiveness.

Njuguna, Muli and Wainaina (2021).evaluated mediating influence of collective bargaining and employee effectiveness in water service providers in Murang'a County. The study was guided by three objectives; The study embraced an exploratory research design. A sample of 206 employees was selected from five water service providers namely: Murang'a Water and Sanitation Company Limited, Murang'a South Water and Sanitation Company Limited, Gatanga Water and Sanitation Company Limited, Gatamathi Water and Sanitation Company Limited and Kahuti Water and Sanitation Company Limited. Random sampling was applied in picking the respondents for the study. Self-administered questionnaires aided in collecting primary data and analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. A pilot study was steered on data collection tool to pre-test its validity prior to the main survey. Data reliability was measured using Cronbach's alpha coefficient. Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 21.0 was used to aid in coding, entry and analysis of data. The study concludes that participatory management

through collective bargaining in management, quality circles, representative participation and delegation is vital and significantly affects productivity of employees in water service providers in Murang'a County, Kenya. However, the study finally concludes that through collective bargaining failed to mediate the relationship between participatory management and employees' effectiveness. Collective bargaining therefore played insignificant part in enhancing effectiveness of participatory management to enhance employees' productivity.

Oyo-Ita, Worlu and Udoh (2020) examined the impact of employee delegation participatory management on production timelines in selected banks in Lagos State. The central objective of the study is to examine the significant relationship between employee delegation participatory management and production timelines. A survey research design was employed for the study. The sample for the study comprised 220 staff from some selected banks. Regression analysis was used to measure the relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variables. SPSS was also adopted for the research in testing the research hypotheses. The results of the findings showed that there is a positive relationship between participatory management and production timelines. The study concludes that participatory management has the ability to align employees with the system of the organization which will result in production timelines in the organization. Based on the results, the study recommended that organizations should increase the intensity of involving employees in the decision making process for goals to be achieved faster and employees should be carried along in the strategic plans of organizations for better profitability. Zang Abba and Hamid, (2020) investigated employee delegation participation in decision making as a motivational factor for building high production timelines in the organization. Data were generated by means of a Five (5) points modified Likert scale, questionnaires; distributed to 120 employees of three (3) manufacturing companies in Nigeria. Responses from the survey were statistically analyzed using multiple regression analysis and statistics of percentages to answer the research questions; and correlation coefficient and multiple regression analysis to verify the assertions of the hypotheses. The results of the study indicated a statistically substantial relationship between employee delegation in decision making and motivation for high production timelines in the workplace. The study concludes that management should identify the circles of decisions (Forms, Stages and Levels); determine the scope of employee delegation, and encourage employees in participative management to enhance production timelines.

METHODOLOGY

Descriptive survey research strategy was employed so as to precisely capture the respondents' views and opinion. Descriptive study is advantageous because it determines and reports the way things are. It describes possible behaviour, attitudes, values and characteristics. Mandyata (2015) adds that descriptive design is reflective and accommodative to the human mind. This study was carried out in Anambra State. Anambra State is a Nigerian state, located in the southeastern region of the country. This study made use of primary data. The primary source of data is the use of questionnaire to collect data on first hand basis. They are firsthand information specially collected for the study. The population of study comprise 1648 employee of plastic manufacturing firms in Anambra State, Nigeria. The sample size consist 321 employee of employee of plastic manufacturing firms in Anambra State, Nigeria using statistical formular devised by Borg and Gall (1973). For the purpose of data collection, the researcher makes use of a structured questionnaire. In the structured questionnaire, participants were required to respond to options which range from Strongly Agree (5), Agree (4), Undecided (3), Disagree (2) Strongly Disagree (1). Face and content validity approach was adopted. Test re-test method and Cronbach Alpha was carried out to achieve reliability. Simple percentage analysis was employed to answer the research questions. Linear regression analysis was conducted to assess the relative predictive power of the independent variables on the dependent variable. The statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) version 23 was employed to test the hypotheses.

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

In this section, the data generated from the employee of the sampled plastic firms were presented, analyzed and interpreted.

Questionnaire Distribution Analysis

Table 1: Questionnaire Response Rate

ITEMS DISTRIBUTED	NUMBER	PERCENTAGE
Copies of the questionnaire distributed	321	100
Copies of the questionnaire Returned	300	100
Copies of valid questionnaire	300	93.5
Copies of the questionnaire not returned	21	6.5
Total	300	100

Author’s compilation 2025

A total of three hundred and twenty one (321) copies of the questionnaire were distributed to the employees of the selected plastic firms. A total of three hundred (300) copies were retrieved from the respondents. The researcher worked with the three hundred (300) copies retrieved.

Presentation of Data relevant to the Research Questions

Research Question 1: *To what extent does employees’ consultation affect employee effectiveness in plastic manufacturing firms in Anambra State, Nigeria?*

Table 2: Respondents' view on the effect of employees’ consultation affect employee effectiveness in plastic manufacturing firms

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
Agree	111	38	38
Strongly Agree	151	50	50
Neutral	30	10	10
Disagree	4	1	1
Strongly Disagree	4	1	1
Total	300	100	100

Source: Field Survey, 2025/SPSS

Table 2 reveals that 50% of the respondents strongly agree that employees’ consultation affect employee effectiveness in plastic manufacturing firms 1% agree, 10% are neutral, 1% disagree while 38% of respondents disagree.

Research Question 2: *To what degree does employees’ collective bargaining influence employee efficacy in plastic manufacturing firms in Anambra State, Nigeria?*

Table 3: Respondents' opinion on whether employees’ collective bargaining influence employee efficacy in plastic manufacturing firm

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
Agree	161	54	54
Strongly Agree	93	31	31
Neutral	22	7	7
Disagree	14	5	5
Strongly Disagree	10	3	3
Total	300	100	100

Source: Field Survey, 2025 /SPSS

Table 2 shows that greater percentages 31%of respondents agree that employees’ collective bargaining influence employee efficacy in plastic manufacturing firms, 56.3 % strongly agree, 7.3% are neutral, 3.3% disagree while 4.6%of respondents strongly disagree.

Research Question 3: *To what extent does employee delegation influence product timelines in plastic manufacturing firms in Anambra State, Nigeria?*

Table 4.3.11: Respondents view on whether employee delegation influence product timelines in plastic manufacturing firms

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
Agree	208	69	69
Strongly Agree	69	23	23
Neutral	10	3	3
Strongly Disagree	5	2	2
Disagree	8	3	3
Total	300	100	100

Source: Field Survey, 2025 /SPSS

Table 4.311 reveals that greater percentages of 69% of respondents agree that employee delegation influence product timelines in plastic manufacturing firms, 23% strongly agree, 3 % are neutral, 3% disagree while 2% of respondents strongly disagree.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One

Ho: Employee consultation has no significance effect on employee effectiveness in plastic manufacturing firms in Anambra State, Nigeria.

Hi: Employee consultation has a significance effect on employee effectiveness in plastic manufacturing firms in Anambra State, Nigeria.

	Model	Coefficients ^a			t	Sig.
		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	Employee Effectiveness	.696	.052		13.324	.000
	Employees consultation	.976	.017	.935	56.187	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Effectiveness

Interpretation: With the linear regression model, the error of estimate is low, with a value of about .51439. The Durbin Watson statistics of 0.080, which is not more than 2, indicates there is no autocorrelation. The employees' consultation coefficient of 0.935 indicates a positive significance between employees' consultation and employee effectiveness, which is statistically significant (with t = 56.187 with p= .000). Therefore, the null hypothesis should be rejected and the alternative hypothesis accordingly accepted. Employee consultation has a significance effect on employee effectiveness in plastic manufacturing firms in Anambra State, Nigeria

Hypothesis Two

Ho: Collective bargaining as an essential right of workers has no significant effect on employee efficacy in plastic manufacturing firms in Anambra State, Nigeria.

Hi: Collective bargaining has a significant effect on employee efficacy in plastic manufacturing firms in Anambra State, Nigeria.

	Model	Coefficients ^a			t	Sig.
		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	Employee Efficacy	.674	.080		8.416	.000
	Collective Bargaining	.753	.044	.627	17.220	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Efficacy

Interpretation: With the linear regression model, the error of estimate is low, with a value of about .03514. The Durbin Watson statistics of 0.080, which is not more than 2, indicates there is no autocorrelation. The collective bargaining coefficient of 0.627 indicates a positive significance between collective bargaining and employee efficacy, which is statistically significant (with t = 17.220 with p =

.000). Therefore, the null hypothesis should be rejected and the alternative hypothesis accordingly accepted. Collective bargaining has a significant effect on employee efficacy in plastic manufacturing firms in Anambra State, Nigeria.

Hypothesis Three

Ho: Employee delegation has no significant influence on production timelines in plastic manufacturing firms in Anambra State, Nigeria.

Hi: Employee delegation has a significant influence on production timelines in plastic manufacturing firms in Anambra State, Nigeria.

Model	Coefficients ^a			t	Sig.
	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 Production Timelines	-.447	.031		-14.324	.000
Employee delegation	.411	.022	.287	18.561	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Production Timelines

Interpretation: With the linear regression model, the error of estimate is low, with a value of about .24104. The Durbin Watson statistics of 0.162, which is not more than 2, indicates there is no autocorrelation. The employee delegation coefficient of 0.987 indicates a positive significance between employee delegation and production timelines, which is statistically significant (with $t = 18.561$ with $p = .000$). Therefore, the null hypothesis should be rejected and the alternative hypothesis accordingly accepted. Then we can state that employee delegation has a significant influence on production timelines in plastic manufacturing firms in Anambra State, Nigeria.

Summary of Findings

1. Employee consultation has a significance effect on employee effectiveness in plastic manufacturing firms in Anambra State, Nigeria. (with $t = 56.187$ with $p = .000$).
2. Collective bargaining has a significant effect on employee efficacy in plastic manufacturing firms in Anambra State, Nigeria. ($t = 17.220$, $p = .000$).
3. Employee delegation has a significant influence on production timelines in plastic manufacturing firms in Anambra State, Nigeria. ($t = 18.561$, $p = .000$).

CONCLUSION

This study examined employee participation on decision making and organizational productivity using plastic manufacturing Firms in Anambra State, Nigeria. Data were sourced from plastic manufacturing Firms in Anambra State. The data generated were analyzed using liner regression analysis and the result shows that employee consultation has a significance effect on employee effectiveness; collective bargaining has a significant effect on employee efficacy; employee delegation has a significant influence on production timelines; therefore, the study concluded that employee participation on decision had a positive significant effect on employee productivity

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the result of the findings and conclusion, the following recommendations were necessary:

1. Management of plastic manufacturing should make it a part of its standard policy to ensure all employee opinions, suggestions, view are subjected to their merit and accepted where applicable after employee' consultation.
2. Management and employee of plastic manufacturing should explore options together; and collective bargaining should reconsider their strategies for engagement in order to enhance their relationship

3. Employee should be delegated to make contribution in policy development as they play a major role in policy implementation and this among others will increase organizational productivity through employee delegation.

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